

This is a link to the data repository refubium, which hosts the experimental data and the code used in the paper "Probing resonant Andreev reflections by photon-assisted tunneling at the atomic scale" by Olof Peters, Nils Bogdanoff, Sergio Acero Gonzalez, Larissa Melischek, J. Rika Simon, Gaël Reecht, Clemens B. Winkelmann, Felix von Oppen and Katharina J. Franke, published in Nature Physics 16, 1222 (2020):

<https://refubium.fu-berlin.de/handle/fub188/29997>